

Tourette Syndrome

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Abstract

Tourette Syndrome (TS) is a neurodevelopmental disorder characterized by the presence of multiple motor and vocal tics. The disorder is named after the French neurologist Georges Gilles de la Tourette who first described the condition in 1885. TS is a complex disorder that affects a wide range of individuals, with symptoms varying in severity and presentation. The exact cause of the disorder is not fully understood, but research suggests that a combination of genetic and environmental factors may play a role in its development. Recent genetic studies have identified several genes that may be associated with the development of TS. The most well-known of these genes is the gene for the dopamine receptor D1 (DRD1). This gene has been found to be more common in individuals with TS, suggesting that a dysfunction in the dopamine system may play a role in the disorder. Other genes that have been associated with TS include those involved in the regulation of neurotransmitters such as serotonin and GABA, as well as genes involved in the immune system and neurodevelopment. Another area of research in TS is the relationship between the immune system and the nervous system, known as neuroimmunology. Studies have suggested that infections, particularly those that

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affect the nervous system, may be a potential trigger for the onset or exacerbation of tic symptoms in individuals with TS. Additionally, research has found that individuals with TS have elevated levels of certain immune markers such as cytokines and antibodies. Other factors that have been identified as potentially contributing to the development of TS include stress, exposure to toxins and pollutants, obesity and metabolic disorders, trauma and head injuries, and gut microbiome. The relationship between these factors and TS is complex

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and not fully understood, and they may interact with each other and with genetic factors in ways that are not yet understood. The diagnostic classification of TS can be challenging due to the wide range of symptoms and severity that can be observed in individuals with the disorder. The current diagnostic criteria for TS are outlined in the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, Fifth Edition (DSM-5). The diagnosis is typically made by a healthcare professional, such as a neurologist or psychiatrist, who will take a detailed history of the individual's symptoms and conduct a thorough physical and neurological examination. It is important to note that while TS is a complex disorder, many individuals with TS can manage their symptoms with a combination of medications, behavioral therapies, and other interventions. Additionally, TS does not have a significant impact on overall intelligence or lifespan, and most individuals with TS lead productive and fulfilling lives.

Keywords: *Tourette Syndrome, Neurodevelopmental Disorder, Immune System*

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I. INTRODUCTION

Tourette's Disorder (TD) is a neuropsychiatric disorder characterized by motor and vocal tics that appear in childhood. It is defined as sudden, repetitive movements, gestures and sounds made in a certain pattern. Although it is seen that tics can start between the ages of 2 and 21, it is considered to start around the age of 5-7 on average and reaches an intense and severe level around the age of 12. The onset of vocal tics often occurs several years after motor tics. Although the frequency of studies varies; In recent studies, its incidence has been shown to be approximately 1%, with a male/female ratio of 3/1 between the ages of 5-18 (Robertson et al., 2009). Tics can be simple or complex, suppressed temporarily, and some children may describe a sensory discomfort before the tic. TD does not show ethnic and sociocultural differences in terms of clinical features. It is known that genetic and familial factors are important in the etiology of TD, but the genetic basis has not yet been fully elucidated (Robertson et al., 2009).

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2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Definition and History

Tourette's Disorder (TD) is a neurodevelopmental disorder characterized by motor and vocal tics that appear in childhood. It is defined as sudden, repetitive movements, gestures and sounds made in a certain pattern. Although it is seen that tics can start between the ages of 2 and 21, it is considered to start around the age of 5 to 7 on average and reaches an intense and severe level around the age of 12. The onset of vocal tics often occurs several years after motor tics. Most of the cases are accompanied by behavioral problems. These; attention deficit and hyperactivity disorder (ADHD), obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD), mood disorders, impulse control disorders and repetitive tic-like symptoms (such as self-harming behaviors) and socially inappropriate behaviors (Cavanna et al., 2009). These behavioral problems may become more dominant in the clinical picture of some patients and cause more loss of functionality than tics.

While it is possible to see examples of Tourette's syndrome mentioned in the literature since ancient times, the first described case is the Marquise de Dampierre case of the French neurologist Itard in 1825 (Newman, 2010). About 50 years later, the first systematic review and description was made in 1885 by the French neurologist Gilles De la Tourette, one of Charcot's students, with a series of 9 cases. He also mentioned that the disease, which he defined as meaningless shouting (later defined as vocal tic), echolalia, coprolalia, and accompanying behavioral problems, in addition to tics that started in childhood, is associated with obsessive-compulsive disorder, and shows familial characteristics (Bloch and Leckman, 2007).

In the past, TD was thought to be a very rare psychological disease; This

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perspective began to change in the 1960s, with the discovery of antipsychotics and the emergence of beneficial results in the treatment of tics in individuals with

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TD. The hypothesis that TD may be a neurological disease that may result from a disorder in the brain gained weight, and studies were focused on elucidating the underlying neurobiological and genetic basis (Bloch and Leckman, 2007). In the DSM-3 published in 1980, the diagnostic criteria were determined and classified as a separate diagnosis under the title of 'tic disorders'. In the first defined criteria, Beginning between the ages of 2 and 15, rapid, repetitive, purposeless, and involuntary motor movements affecting many different muscle groups, multiple vocal tics, movements can be suppressed voluntarily for minutes or hours, the intensity of the symptoms varies between weeks and months, it had a long duration. In the following years, the diagnostic criteria were developed and modified, and it was finalized in the DSM-5 published in May 2013 (Robertson & Eapen, 2014).

Today, more comprehensive, and different information about TD has been obtained than the first definition of Gilles De la Tourette. In addition, success is achieved in its treatment with both pharmacological, psychological, and even surgical treatments.

2.2. Epidemiology

TD is a common disorder of all social classes and races worldwide. Most case reports meeting the current diagnostic criteria in the literature were from the USA, Europe, New Zealand, Brazil, China, and the Middle East. The fact that the clinical features of the cases are very similar supports that TD does not differ ethnically and culturally and originates from a common genetic basis.

While TD was thought to be a very rare condition in previous years; It is known to be a more common condition nowadays. In the prevalence study of Burd et al. in 1986; The frequency of clinically determined TD in school-aged children has been reported as 5/10,000 (Burd et al., 1986). A lot of work has been

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done in the last 20 years. Although there are results showing that TD varies between 0.04% and 3.8% in the population; it is generally accepted that the population frequency is 1% and the female/male ratio is 3-4/1 (Robertson, Eapen, and Cavanna, 2009). As a matter of fact, in a meta-analysis of 21 population- based prevalence studies published by Scharf et al. in 2015, they found the prevalence of TD in the community to be 0.52% (Scharf et al. 2015). The prevalence is higher in children with special educational needs such as autism spectrum disorder, learning disorder, emotional and behavioral problems (Robertson, Eapen and Cavanna, 2009).

There are various reasons for such variability in studies on its incidence in the population. First reason; The frequency and severity of tic disorders vary according to age (as the incidence increases in school age and starts to decrease in adolescence). Secondly, Methodological differences in studies conducted and, finally, changes in TD diagnostic criteria over time are considered as reasons (Bloch and Leckman, 2007).

TD: It is a condition that begins in childhood and is more common in children and adolescents than in adults. In cases diagnosed in adulthood, it has been reported that symptoms often begin in childhood. Usually, symptoms begin around the age of 7 in the child with TD and decrease or disappear during adolescence or adulthood. The pathophysiology of this reduction in symptoms is still not understood.

2.3. Pathophysiology

The exact pathophysiological mechanisms of TD have not been clearly demonstrated yet. Recent studies confirm the hypothesis that TD is an inherited and developmental disorder of interneuron synaptic transmission (Jankovic, 2001).

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Today, neurobiological research is focused on elucidating the psychological and cellular mechanisms underlying tics and TD, and many

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different studies are carried out examining brain structures and physiology. But these are They cannot be compared with each other since they use different methods, have small samples or other undetermined reasons. Some of these studies will be discussed in more detail below.

Today, in TD neurobiology, In addition to disinhibition of the cortico-striatal-thalamic-cortical pathway, it is accepted that increased caduate nucleus activity plays a role (Singer 2005, 2011). It is assumed that similar models apply to ADHD and OCD. Dysfunction in this pathway is thought to result in the inability to suppress unwanted movements, behaviors, and impulsivity.

It is known that many neurotransmitters play an active role in the pathophysiology of TD. However, dopamine is particularly prominent because the symptoms respond to drugs that act on dopamine receptors. Functional neuroimaging studies show abnormalities in dopaminergic systems in the striatum and cortex. In patients with TD, An increase in presynaptic dopamine transporter and postsynaptic D2 dopamine receptor density, which supports an increase in dopamine release and reuptake, has been detected (Felling and Singer 2011; Liu et al., 2010).

Increased dopamine density has led some researchers to develop the idea that the tic phenotype and other TD-related behaviors are related to dopamine hypersensitivity in the striatum, prefrontal cortex, and motor areas. This dopamine hypersensitivity hypothesis may explain why tics respond to antidopaminergic agents in the treatment (Hawley, 2011).

Functional neuroimaging studies in the presence of active tics have shown multifocal activation in many regions of the brain. These regions are: Medial and lateral premotor cortices, anterior cingulate cortex, dorsolateral-rostral prefrontal cortex, inferior prefrontal cortex, putamen, caudate nucleus, primary motor cortex, Broca's area, superior temporal gyrus, insula, and clostrum. It has been determined

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that the formation of tics and the activation of these regions are simultaneous. It has been observed that this common and abnormal activity is in

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interrelated pathways such as sensorimotor, tongue and paralimbic regions (Bohlhalter et al., 2006).

The basal ganglia (especially the caudate nucleus) and the inferior prefrontal cortex have been found to play an important role in the pathogenesis of TD. In volumetric magnetic resonance imaging studies, Children with TD have been found to have wider dorsolateral prefrontal regions and increase in cortical white matter in the right frontal lobe. In another study, It was found that caudate volume was significantly negatively correlated with tic severity and OCD in measurements performed before the first 14 years of age and 7.5 years later (Bloch et al. 2005).

2.4. Etiology

Factors thought to be involved in the etiology of TD; genetic causes, infectious and neuroimmunological factors, prenatal and perinatal difficulties, psychosocial factors, and androgen exposure. Although TD was thought to be a psychological condition in the past, this theory has now been completely abandoned.

2.4.1. Genetic Factors

Tourette Syndrome (TS) is a neurodevelopmental disorder characterized by the presence of multiple motor and vocal tics. The onset of tics typically occurs in childhood and the severity of symptoms can vary greatly from person to person. While the exact cause of TS is not fully understood, research suggests that a combination of genetic and environmental factors may play a role in its development. Recent genetic studies have identified several genes that may be associated with the development of TS. The most well-known of these genes is the gene for the dopamine receptor D1 (DRD1). This gene has been found to be

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more common in individuals with TS, suggesting that a dysfunction in the dopamine system may play a role in the disorder. Other genes that have been associated with TS include those involved in the regulation of neurotransmitters such as serotonin and GABA, as well as genes involved in the immune system and neurodevelopment (O'Rourke et. al. 2009).

Several genetic variations have been identified as potential risk factors for TS. One such variation is a duplication on chromosome 2q31, which has been found in a subset of individuals with TS. This duplication is thought to disrupt the normal function of several genes in the region, potentially leading to the development of tics. Other genetic variations that have been associated with TS include those in the genes SLITRK1 and HDC. The relationship between genetics and TS is complex and not fully understood. It is likely that multiple genes and genetic variations contribute to the development of the disorder, and that their effects may be influenced by environmental factors such as stress, infection, or trauma. Additionally, the genetic factors that contribute to TS may vary from person to person, leading to the wide range of symptoms and severity observed in individuals with the disorder (Leckman, 2002).

While genetic factors clearly play a role in the development of TS, it is important to note that they do not necessarily determine the outcome of the disorder. Many individuals with TS can manage their symptoms with a combination of medications, behavioral therapies, and other interventions. Additionally, TS does not have a significant impact on overall intelligence or lifespan, and most individuals with TS lead productive and fulfilling lives. In conclusion, genetic factors play a significant role in the development of Tourette Syndrome. Multiple genes and genetic variations have been associated with the disorder, with the dopamine receptor D1 gene being the most well-known. However, the relationship between genetics and TS is complex and not fully understood. Environmental

factors may also play a role in its development. The genetic factors that contribute

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to TS may vary from person to person, leading to the wide range of symptoms and severity observed in individuals with the

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disorder. With the ongoing research, the genetic factors of the disorder will be better understood which will help in the development of new treatments for the disorder (O'Rourke et.al 2009).

2.4.2. Neuroimmunology and Infections

While the exact cause of TS is not fully understood, research suggests that a combination of genetic and environmental factors may play a role in its development. One area of increasing interest in the field of TS research is the relationship between the immune system and the nervous system, known as neuroimmunology. The effect of infections on TS is one aspect of this research that has gained attention in recent years. The immune system plays a crucial role in protecting the body from harmful pathogens and maintaining overall health. However, a dysfunction in the immune system can lead to a range of disorders, including those that affect the nervous system. Research has suggested that the immune system may be involved in the development of TS, as individuals with the disorder have been found to have elevated levels of certain immune markers such as cytokines and antibodies. Infections, particularly those that affect the nervous system, have been found to be a potential trigger for the onset or exacerbation of tic symptoms in individuals with TS. Studies have shown that individuals with TS have a higher rate of infections, particularly upper respiratory tract infections, compared to the general population. Additionally, the onset or worsening of tic symptoms has been reported in many individuals with TS following an infection (Hoekstra et.al, 2004).

One theory is that infections may trigger an immune response that leads to inflammation in the brain, which in turn causes changes in neurotransmitter systems such as dopamine, which is thought to play a role in the development of tics. This theory is supported by evidence that certain anti-inflammatory medications, such

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as non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) and

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corticosteroids, can improve tic symptoms in some individuals with TS. Another theory is that infections may cause a dysfunction in the immune system which leads to the production of autoantibodies against specific proteins in the brain, resulting in tic symptoms. Studies have shown that individuals with TS have a higher rate of autoantibodies against certain proteins, such as dopamine receptors and tubulin, which are involved in the development of tics (Martino et.al 2015).

It is also important to note that the relationship between infections and TS is likely complex and not fully understood. Other factors such as genetics, stress, and environmental exposures may also play a role in the development of the disorder and the exacerbation of symptoms. In conclusion, the field of neuroimmunology is an increasingly important area of research in Tourette Syndrome (TS). Studies have suggested that infections, particularly those that affect the nervous system, may be a potential trigger for the onset or exacerbation of tic symptoms in individuals with TS. The relationship between infections and TS is likely complex and not fully understood, other factors such as genetics, stress and environmental exposures may also play a role in the development of the disorder and the exacerbation of symptoms. The ongoing research in this field may lead to a better understanding of the disorder and the development of new treatments (Jankovic, 2020).

2.5. Other Causes

While the exact cause of TS is not fully understood, research suggests that a combination of genetic and environmental factors may play a role in its development. While genetics and infections are known to be associated with the disorder, there are other factors that have been identified that may also contribute to the development of TS. One such factor is stress. Stress has been found to be a common trigger for tic symptoms in individuals with TS, with many reporting that

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their tics worsen during periods of high stress. Research has suggested that stress

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may cause changes in the levels of certain neurotransmitters, such as dopamine and serotonin, which play a role in the development of tics. Additionally, stress may also lead to changes in the immune system, which may also contribute to the development of tics. Another factor that may contribute to the development of TS is exposure to toxins and pollutants. Studies have found that individuals with TS have a higher rate of exposure to certain toxins, such as pesticides and heavy metals, compared to the general population. These toxins may cause changes in the brain and the immune system, leading to the development of tics (Jankovic & Kurlan, 2011).

Obesity and metabolic disorders are also suggested to be associated with TS. Studies have shown that individuals with TS are more likely to be overweight or obese, and that this may contribute to the development of tics. Additionally, metabolic disorders such as diabetes and metabolic syndrome have been found to be more common in individuals with TS and may also contribute to the development of the disorder (Comings & Comings, 1990).

Trauma and head injuries have also been suggested as a possible risk factor for TS. Studies have found that individuals with TS are more likely to have a history of head injuries or traumatic events, and that this may contribute to the development of tics. This may be due to changes in the brain caused by the injury or trauma, or to changes in the immune system. Lastly, the gut microbiome, which is the collection of microorganisms that live in the digestive tract, has also been suggested as a possible factor in the development of TS. Studies have found that individuals with TS have a different gut microbiome compared to the general population, and that this may contribute to the development of tics. This may be due to changes in the immune system or changes in the production of certain neurotransmitters (Jankovic & Kurlan, 2011).

It is important to note that the relationship between these factors and TS is

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complex and not fully understood. Additionally, these factors may interact with each other and with genetic factors in ways that are not yet understood. It is also

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important to note that these factors do not necessarily determine the outcome of the disorder, and many individuals with TS are able to manage their symptoms with a combination of medications, behavioral therapies, and other interventions. In conclusion, while genetics and infections are known to be associated with Tourette Syndrome (TS), there are other factors that have been identified that may also contribute to the development of the disorder. These factors include stress, exposure to toxins and pollutants, obesity and metabolic disorders, trauma and head injuries, and gut microbiome. The relationship between these factors and TS is complex and not fully understood. Additionally, these factors may interact with each other and with genetic factors in ways that are not yet understood. Ongoing research may provide a better understanding of the disorder and the development of new treatments (Jankovic, 2001).

2.6. Diagnostic Classification

The diagnosis of TS can be complex and challenging due to the wide range of symptoms and severity that can be observed in individuals with the disorder. The diagnostic classification of TS has evolved over time and continues to be refined as new research emerges. The current diagnostic criteria for TS are outlined in the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, Fifth Edition (DSM-5). To be diagnosed with TS, an individual must have had multiple motor and/or vocal tics for at least one year, with the onset of symptoms before the age of 18. The tics must also cause significant impairment in social, academic, or occupational functioning. Additionally, the individual must not have a history of a tic-free period of more than three consecutive months (Nielsen et.al, 2020).

The diagnosis of TS is typically made by a healthcare professional, such as a neurologist or psychiatrist, who will take a detailed history of the individual's symptoms and conduct a thorough physical and neurological examination.

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Additionally, the healthcare professional may also use rating scales, such as the

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Yale Global Tic Severity Scale or the Tourette Syndrome Symptom List, to evaluate the severity of the individual's tics. The diagnosis of TS can also be challenging in cases where the individual has comorbid conditions, such as attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) or obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD). These conditions often occur alongside TS and can make the diagnosis more difficult. In such cases, a thorough assessment of the individual's symptoms and a detailed medical history are crucial to make a correct diagnosis (Cortese et. al 2008).

Additionally, the diagnosis of TS can be challenging in cases where the individual has mild or infrequent tics. In such cases, a diagnosis of provisional tic disorder or persistent (chronic) motor or vocal tic disorder may be made. These disorders are subthreshold versions of TS, meaning that the individual has some, but not all, of the symptoms of TS. Another diagnostic classification system used for TS is the Global Clinical Assessment of Tic Severity (G-CATS) which is based on the criteria of the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, Fifth Edition (DSM-5). G-CATS is a clinical assessment system that uses a combination of clinical examination and rating scales to classify the severity of tics in individuals with TS. In conclusion, the diagnostic classification of Tourette Syndrome (TS) is based on the criteria outlined in the DSM-5. To be diagnosed with TS, an individual must have had multiple motor and/or vocal tics for at least one year, with the onset of symptoms before the age of 18. The tics must also cause significant impairment in social, academic, or occupational functioning. The diagnosis can be challenging in cases where the individual has comorbid conditions or mild or infrequent tics. The Global Clinical Assessment of Tic Severity (G-CATS) is another diagnostic classification system used for TS. The ongoing research in the field may lead to better diagnostic tools and a better understanding of the disorder (Hallett, 2015).

3. CONCLUSION

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Tourette Syndrome (TS) is a neurodevelopmental disorder characterized by the presence of multiple motor and vocal tics. The disorder is named after the French neurologist Georges Gilles de la Tourette who first described the condition in 1885. TS is a complex disorder that affects a wide range of individuals, with symptoms varying in severity and presentation. The exact cause of the disorder is not fully understood, but research suggests that a combination of genetic and environmental factors may play a role in its development.

Genetics has been identified as a significant contributing factor in the development of TS. Studies have identified several genes that may be associated with the disorder, with the dopamine receptor D1 gene being the most well-known. However, it is important to note that the relationship between genetics and TS is complex and not fully understood.

Another important area of research in TS is the relationship between the immune system and the nervous system, known as neuroimmunology. Studies have suggested that infections, particularly those that affect the nervous system, may be a potential trigger for the onset or exacerbation of tic symptoms in individuals with TS. Additionally, research has found that individuals with TS have elevated levels of certain immune markers such as cytokines and antibodies.

Other factors that have been identified as potentially contributing to the development of TS include stress, exposure to toxins and pollutants, obesity and metabolic disorders, trauma and head injuries, and gut microbiome. The relationship between these factors and TS is complex and not fully understood, and they may interact with each other and with genetic factors in ways that are not yet understood.

The diagnostic classification of TS can be challenging due to the wide range of symptoms and severity that can be observed in individuals with the disorder. The **THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE**

current diagnostic criteria for TS are outlined in the Diagn and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, Fifth Edition (DSM-5). The diagnosis is

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typically made by a healthcare professional, such as a neurologist or psychiatrist, who will take a detailed history of the individual's symptoms and conduct a thorough physical and neurological examination.

It is important to note that while TS is a complex disorder, many individuals with TS can manage their symptoms with a combination of medications, behavioral therapies, and other interventions. Additionally, TS does not have a significant impact on overall intelligence or lifespan, and most individuals with TS lead productive and fulfilling lives.

In conclusion, Tourette Syndrome (TS) is a neurodevelopmental disorder characterized by the presence of multiple motor and vocal tics. The exact cause of the disorder is not fully understood, but research suggests that a combination of genetic and environmental factors may play a role in its development. Genetics, neuroimmunology and other factors such as stress, exposure to toxins and pollutants, obesity and metabolic disorders, trauma and head injuries, and gut microbiome are important areas of research that may lead to a better understanding of the disorder and the development of new treatments. The diagnostic classification of the disorder can be challenging, but with the ongoing research, the diagnostic tools are improving. Despite the complexity of the disorder, many individuals with TS can manage their symptoms and lead productive and fulfilling lives.

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